

Synthesis and Characterisation of New Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes of Acid Hydrazides

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Dioxouranium(VI) complexes of some aliphatic (mono, di), aromatic and heterocyclic hydrazides have been prepared in presence or absence of NaOAc and characterised. The ligands coordinate in a mono-, bi-, tri- and/or tetradentate fashion in the enol except that derived from adipic acid dihydrazide which is bonded through keto form. The existence of a dihydroxo-bridges for the complexes isolated in the presence of NaOAc or basic medium (N₂H₄) is confirmed. Also, the relation between the colour and stability of complexes with the mode of chelation as well as the side-chain attached to the donor sites is discussed.

In continuation of our earlier work¹ on dioxouranium(VI) complexes derived from ligands containing ON or ONO as a donor sites, we report herein the preparation and characterisation of some complexes derived from acid hydrazides. Few papers² have been published concerning these ligands with actinide metal ions, especially with uranyl ion. The aim of the present work is to shed some light on the relation between the mode of chelation and some physical properties, to investigate the role of NaOAc on the formation of dihydroxo-bridges and, finally, to fill the gap between our earlier work and the literature.

Results and Discussion

Different kinds of dioxouranium(VI) complexes derived from some acid hydrazides have been prepared (Table I). Compounds of types I–III (Table I) involve one mole of ligand, either in the deprotonated form (I and II) or the neutral form (III), per UO₂²⁺ ion. Compound of the type IV has two moles of the deprotonated OXD per UO₂²⁺ while V and VI have one mole of deprotonated ligands per two UO₂²⁺ ions. The difference between V and VI is that V has been prepared in EtOH while VI prepared in the presence of ethanolic solution containing dilute N₂H₄ (pH ≈ 8). Compounds of the type VII involve a dimeric structure through dihydroxo-bridges and have been prepared in the presence of NaOAc. Both types VI and VII have been prepared in a basic medium and contain dihydroxo-bridges.

They bear marked resemblance except that the acetate group in VI has been replaced by another mole of ligand (VII).

All the dioxouranium(VI) complexes are air-stable and insoluble in most common organic solvents but easily soluble in dimethylformamide (DMF). The molar conductivities of all complexes except those of GT and GP in DMF at 25° are in the range 3–17.5 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicating a non-electrolytic nature¹. The comparatively high values (34.36 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) of GT and GP complexes are mainly due to the presence of one ionisable chloride ion in the free ligands⁵ as well as its metal complexes. The high melting points (>280°) for all the complexes except that derived from ADH together with the insolubility of the yellow and/or orange complexes suggest either a dimeric structure through dihydroxo-bridges or the existence of a strong covalent bonding or both. The yellow colour of the complexes is mainly attributed to the absence of conjugated system and partially to charge transfer (UO₂²⁺ → L). On the other hand, the orange colour for the two complexes derived from SH and OXD is attributed to the existence of a conjugated systems (Ph–C=N–) in the former and (–N=C–C=O) in the latter. Also, the existence of charge transfer (L → UO₂²⁺) is another factor for the orange colour. The low melting point (162°) for the complex derived from ADH suggests a simple coordination via keto form. The magnetic data indicate

that the complexes are diamagnetic as expected for a f^0 -system.

The ir spectra of all the ligands show broad bands centered at 3 260–3 480 (NH_2) and 3 160–3 240 cm^{-1} (NH) of the hydrazide moiety. An additional band at

$\sim 3 420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectrum of MaH is assigned to ν_{OH} vibration. The existence of this band at lower wavenumber together with the observation of a shoulder at 1 720 cm^{-1} indicates the existence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Also, the broadness of both

TABLE I – ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd *	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)					Λ_m^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Type
		C	H	U	N_2H_4	Solvent		
1	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{GT-H})\text{Ac}]$	16.8 (17.0)	3.4 3.3	47.7 48.0	5.5 6.5	—	34.0	I
2.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{GP-H})\text{Ac} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	18.4 (19.0)	2.8 3.2	42.2 41.8	5.3 5.6	5.8 6.3	36.0	I
3.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{MDH-H})\text{Ac}(\text{EtOH})_2] \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{EtOH}$	19.9 (20.7)	3.9 4.3	41.0 40.9	11.6 11.0	3.8 4.0	7.0	I
4	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{CAH-H})\text{Ac}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{EtOH}$	11.5 (12.1)	3.7 2.8	47.8 48.0	6.3 4.6	4.1 4.6	14.0	I
5.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{SH-2H})(\text{EtOH})_2] \cdot \text{EtOH}$	28.4 (28.0)	4.1 4.3	42.9 42.6	6.3 6.3	7.4 8.3	12.0	II
6.	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{ADH})(\text{Ac})_2(\text{EtOH})] \cdot \text{EtOH}$	29.0 (29.0)	5.5 5.6	29.2 28.7	16.3 15.5	4.6 5.5	4.0	III
7	$[\text{UO}_2(\text{OXD-H})_2(\text{EtOH})_2] \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{EtOH}$	17.3 (17.5)	3.6 4.1	38.9 38.4	20.5 20.7	4.5 3.7	3.0	IV
8.	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{OXD-2H})(\text{Ac})_2(\text{EtOH})_2] \cdot \text{EtOH}$	—	—	61.0 (61.5)	8.2 8.3	—	5.0	V
9.	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{FH-H})(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{Ac} \cdot \text{EtOH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \cdot \text{EtOH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	9.7 (10.2)	3.5 2.9	57.1 58.0	3.3 3.9	7.3 7.8	17.5	VI
10.	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{AcH-H})(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{Ac} \cdot \text{EtOH}] \cdot \text{EtOH}$	12.3 (12.2)	2.8 2.8	60.2 59.6	4.0 4.0	6.2 5.8	22	VI
11	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{BuH-H})(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{Ac}(\text{EtOH})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	14.0 (13.9)	3.7 3.5	54.8 55.2	3.6 3.7	3.6 4.2	4.5	VI
12	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{CpH-H})(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{Ac} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	12.0 (11.8)	3.9 3.0	58.3 58.3	3.2 3.9	4.1 4.4	2.6	VI
13.	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{CMH-H})_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{EtOH})_2] \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{EtOH}$	18.6 (18.8)	3.4 3.1	50.6 49.7	—	7.0 7.2	14.0	VII
14	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{MaH-H})_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{EtOH})_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \cdot \text{EtOH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	17.8 (18.3)	3.5 3.8	44.7 45.2	6.0 6.1	5.4 6.1	6.0	VII
15.	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{BH-II})_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{EtOH})_2] \cdot \text{EtOH}$	24.3 (24.4)	2.8 3.5	48.6 48.4	6.0 6.5	3.9 4.7	8.0	VII

*All compounds yellow except sl. no. 5 which is orange; m.p ($^\circ\text{C}$) of all compounds $>280^\circ$ except sl. no. 6 which is 162° **In DMF

NH and NH₂ bands as well as the presence of the amide I band, in the other hydrazides as a shoulder, suggest the existence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Moreover, the nmr spectra of the free ligands in DMSO-d₆ exhibit two signals at δ 9.65–6.05 and 4.85–4.15 (downfield of TMS) assigned to NH and NH₂ respectively. Only the former signal (NH) disappears on adding D₂O. Also, the ir spectra of the free ligands show bands at 1 695–1 640, 1 640–1 610, 1 580–1 535 and 1 260–1 255 cm⁻¹ assigned to amide I, β (NH₂), amide II and amide III bands respectively. Finally, the dihydrazides (MDX, OXD and ADH) show two doublets for NH₂ and NH groups at 3 320–3 260 and 3 220–3 180 cm⁻¹ respectively.

On comparing the ir spectra of the ligands to their uranyl complexes, one observes that the ligands behave in a mono-, bi-, tri-, and/or tetradentate manner toward the uranyl ion. The mode of bonding depends on the sidechain attached to the hydrazide moiety, steric hindrance as well as the medium of the reaction mixture during preparation of the complexes. Also, the spectral data indicate that acetate ion behaves in a bidentate manner.

Firstly, oxaloyldihydrazide (OXD) behaves either as a bidentate (IV) or tetradentate (V) via the enolised carbonyl oxygen and the NH₂ towards one (IV) or two (V) uranyl ions forming a six-membered ring around the metal ion. The orange complex (IV) involves two moles of OXD per uranyl ion while the yellow one (V) contains one mole of OXD per two uranyl ions. Although compound of the type V involving a conjugated system (–N=C–C=N–) is to exert a deep colour but its colour is actually yellow. To explain this phenomenon which is also observed for similar compounds reported earlier¹, we suggest that the H₂O molecule links between the two azomethine groups through hydrogen bonding (V). The existence of the hydrogen bonding depresses to a great extent the resonance process. The main difference between the two types of complexes, i.e. IV and V, is the lack of acetate group in the ir spectra for IV while it exists in V acting in a bidentate manner, where the difference between $\nu_{as}(\text{CO}_2)$ and $\nu_s(\text{CO}_2)$ is quite large (165 cm⁻¹) and falls in the range reported earlier⁶. The observation of splitted bands for each ν_3 , ν_1 and ν_4 vibrations of the O=U=O moiety for compound V as well as the high percentage of ura-

nium are taken as additional evidence for the existence of two uranyl ions. Meanwhile these vibrations are absent in the ir spectrum of IV proving the presence of only one uranyl ion. The mode of chelation in both cases is suggested on the basis of the following evidence : ν_{CO} band disappears, the ν_{NH_2} and β_{NH_2} bands shift to lower wavenumbers, new bands appear at 1 650 (C=N), 1 250 (C–O), 5.15 (UO)⁷ and 370 cm⁻¹ (UN)⁸. Secondly, SH behaves in a tridentate manner via the NH₂, OH(phenolic) and the enolised carbonyl oxygen with replacement of two hydrogen atoms from the latter two groups. The orange colour of the complex [UO₂(SH-2H)(EtOH)₂]EtOH (II) is mainly due to the presence of a resonance structure between the phenyl and the azomethine group. The mode of bonding is supported by the following evidence : disappearance of ν_{OH} (phenolic) and ν_{CO} , the ν_{NH_2} and β_{NH_2} bands shift to lower wavenumbers while $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ band shifts to higher wavenumber. Also new bands appear at 1 630 (C=N), 1 250 (C–O phenolic), 1 150 (C–O hydrazide), 530 (UO)⁷ and 375 cm⁻¹ (UN)⁸.

The existence of EtOH inside and/or outside the coordination sphere is deduced from the nmr and weight-loss data. The nmr data show the OH signal of the bonded ethanol for the complexes at δ 4.6–7.4 region while the OH of the outside ethanol at δ 3.5–4.5 downfield of TMS; the position of the OH (inside the coordination sphere) depends mainly on whether the OH is linked via hydrogen bonding or not. The shifts of the CH₂ and CH₃ signals of ethanol (outside and/or inside) fall more or less in the same region. The observation of one vibration for each ν_3 , ν_1 and ν_4 of the O=U=O moiety in the ir spectrum confirms the presence of only one uranyl ion. Thirdly, maleic acid hydrazide cyclic (CMH) coordinates in a monodentate fashion via the enolised carbonyl oxygen with replacement of a hydrogen atom. CMH can be represented by two tautomeric forms, i.e. keto and enol forms as shown in Fig. 1.

The ir spectrum of the free ligand shows that CMH exists mainly in the keto form which is supported by following facts. Strong ir bands at 3 420 (NH) and 1 735 cm⁻¹ (CO) and nmr proton signal at δ 7.60 (NH) are observed. The presence of NaOAc during complex

formation helps for the creation of dihydroxo-bridges for the complex derived from the CMH (VII). The mode of complexation is supported by the following evidences both ν_{NH} and ν_{CO} bands disappear, the small positive shift of $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ vibration at 990 cm^{-1} and appearance of new bands appear at 1630 (C=N) , 1550 (C-N-O) , 1225 (C-O) and $610 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ (UO)}$.

Fig 1

Also, the complexes with the general formulae $[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{MaH-H})_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{EtOH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{EtOH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{BH-H})_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{EtOH})_2]\text{EtOH}$ were prepared in the presence of NaOAc containing dihydroxo-bridges. The main difference between those complexes and $[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{CMH-H})_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{EtOH})_2] \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{EtOH}$ is that the latter two (Table 1) coordinate in a bidentate manner in which MaH coordinates via the carboxylate group while BH reacts through NH_2 and the enolised carbonyl oxygen. All the complexes containing dihydroxo-bridges have similar IR spectra and especially in the region involving $\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O}$ group.

Finally, all the other remaining ligands coordinate in a bidentate manner in the enol form except ADH and through different potential sites. Complexes of types I and III (Table 1) are quite similar in their mode of chelation except that the latter reacts in the keto form. The ligands coordinate via NH_2 and the enolised carbonyl oxygen. Also, in type VI the ligands coordinate in a bidentate fashion through the above mentioned potential sites but contain dihydroxo-bridges as well as the existence of bidentate acetate (VI).

The visible spectra of all the uranyl complexes in solution (DMSO or nujol) show no bands below $20,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that the complexes have more than four equatorial groups¹⁰. Also, the spectra show a band in the $21,000\text{--}206,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region assignable to $t_2 \rightarrow {}^3\pi$ transition¹. The force constant (k) for

the U-O vibration has been calculated¹² (Table 1). Moreover, the U-O bond distance was calculated using McGlynn method¹³ and the values are in the $1.61\text{--}1.65 \text{ \AA}$ range. These values fall in the same region for those discussed in our earlier work¹.

In conclusion, the complexes containing dihydroxo-bridges are usually synthesised in a basic medium while these with simple structures are obtained in a faintly acidic or neutral solution. The existence of dihydroxo-bridges in the uranyl complexes can be easily identified from ν_3 , ν_1 and ν_4 vibrations of the $\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O}$ moiety in the IR spectra. Also there is a strong relation between the colour of the complexes and charge-transfer which is exerted either from $\text{UO}_2^{2+} \rightarrow \text{L}$ or $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{UO}_2^{2+}$. In the former case, the complexes tend to be yellow in colour while in the latter case a more deep colour is observed. This is true in the absence of conjugated systems or resonance structures. The charge transfer in both cases depends mainly on the type of group attached to the carbonyl oxygen whether the group is releasing or withdrawal. This phenomenon can be generalised for the ligands containing either NO or ONO as a donor site.

Experimental

Ligands 1-3 were prepared using the same technique as reported earlier^{7, 13} except those of pyridinium acetoacetylhydrazide chloride and trimethylaminoacetoacetylhydrazide chloride (GT, m.p. 190°) which were purchased from B.D.H. having general formula $[\text{RCH}_2\text{CONHNH}_2] \cdot \text{Cl}$ (4) $\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ (GP, m.p. 201°), Me_3N , RCONHNH_2 (1) $\text{R} = \text{H}$ (FH, m.p. 54°), Me (AcH, m.p. 67°), $n\text{-Pr}$ (BuH, m.p. 44°), $n\text{-Bu}$ (CpH, m.p. 74.5°), Ph (BH, m.p. 112°), $o\text{-HOC}_6\text{H}_4$ (SH, m.p. 146°), $\text{HO}_2\text{CCH}=\text{CH}$ (MaH, m.p. 128°), $\text{ClCH}_2(\text{CAH}$, m.p. 91°), $\text{NH}_2\text{NHC(O)R}'\text{-(O)CNHNH}_2$ (2) $\text{R}' = \text{zero}$ (OXD, m.p. 235°), CH_2 (MDH, m.p. 154°), $(\text{CH}_2)_4$ (ADH, m.p. 171°), $\text{HC}=\text{C}(\text{O})\text{NHNHC(O)}$ (3) (CMH, m.p. 297°).

Preparation of the complexes All the complexes were prepared by refluxing equimolar (1 mmol) mixture of the uranyl acetate dihydrate and the ligands both in EtOH. The two complexes derived from OXD were prepared using the same procedure but with 1 and 2 mmol for 1:2 and 2:1 (M:L) respectively. NaOAc was used as a buffer in case of CMH, MaH and BH. Also dilute hydrazine was used to raise the

pH of the solution (> 7) in case of FH, AcH, BuH and CpH. The isolated solids were filtered hot, washed with hot EtOH and dried under reduced pressure.

Physical measurements were done as reported earlier¹

References

1. A. YACOUBA-NOUR, A. K. T. MAKI and M. M. MOSTAFA, *Spectrochim. Acta, Sec. A*, 1988, **44**, 1291; *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1990, **15**, 34.
2. R. C. AGGARWAL and B. PRASAD, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 3984; V. KUMARI, S. K. SAHNI, S. KHER and R. N. KAPOOR, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1980, **5**, 85; R. I. LAL, M. N. SINGH and D. DAS, *Syn React. Inorg. Met.-Org. Chem.*, 1986, **16**, 513.
3. T. CURTIUS, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1894, **50**, 280.
4. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
5. A. A. EL-ASMY and M. M. MOSTAFA, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1983, **12**, 291, A. A. EL-ASMY and M. M. MOSTAFA, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 591
6. B. B. KALU and K. B. PANDEYA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **40**, 1035.
7. J. R. FERRARO, "Low Frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum, New York, 1971
8. V. T. ATHVALA and C. S. PADMANABHA-IVIER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 1003
9. M. MASSUI and H. OHMORI, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 153
10. R. G. BHATTACHARYYA and D. C. BERA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 375, V. M. VDOBENDO and A. T. SKOBOLO, *Radiokhimiya*, 1966, **8**, 651
11. C. C. ADDISON, H. A. F. CHAMP, N. HODGE and A. H. NORBURY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2354.
12. L. JONES, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1958, **10**, 395, S. P. MCGLYNN, J. K. SMITH and W. C. NEELY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 105
13. S. P. MCGLYNN and J. K. SMITH, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1961, **6**, 164.
14. R. STOLLE, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1904, **69**, 145; G. PELLIZZARI, *Gazz. Chem. Ital.*, 1894, **24**, 225; T. CURTIUS and F. S. HOFFMANN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1897, **53**, 524; R. STOLLI and G. ZINSSER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1904, **69**, 489, T. CURTIUS, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1894, **50**, 278; C. BULOW and R. WEDLICH, *Chem. Ber.*, 1906, **39**, 3372

